

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF THE INSURANCE MARKET AND ITS DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

Khakberdiyev Bekzod Uktamovich

PhD., Head of the Faculty of Distance and 2nd Higher
Education of the Tashkent State University of Economics

ORCID: 0009-0003-4580-4520

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14564332>

In the conditions of a market economy, the state has made every effort to develop the insurance system, creates a legal framework that facilitates the development of the insurance system, helps to find financial resources for the establishment of insurance companies, and carries out work related to licensing these companies.

An analysis of the literature devoted to the study of the problem of financial stability of an insurance organization allows us to determine that the starting point in determining the essence of financial stability is solvency - "the ability of an insurance company to timely fulfill its monetary obligations, which are based on law or contract".

It should be noted that one of the main external factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies is the legal framework for regulating this system in the country. It is precisely the excellent development of legal and regulatory documents regulating the activities of the insurance market that ensures the effective operation of companies based on the implementation of strategic projects, making optimal decisions, and achieving financial stability.

The basis of any economy depends on its sustainable development. In this case, the effective use of insurance institutions is of great importance. In this regard, ensuring the stability of insurance companies is even more important. One of the main factors ensuring the financial stability of an insurance company is the insurance portfolio. Understanding the essence of the insurance portfolio and ensuring its balanced form remains relevant today. The insurance portfolio is the basis that determines the entire activity of an insurance company and its financial stability. The insurance portfolio is understood as the actual number of insured objects or existing insurance contracts in a certain territory. The financial stability of the insurance portfolio is understood as a constant balance between the risks assumed and the profitability of the portfolio. The size, quality, composition and dynamics of the insurance portfolio determine the profitability of insurance operations, the receipt of insurance payments,

fluctuations in insurance coverage, and changes in the volume of insurance amounts.

An analysis of the literature devoted to the study of the problem of financial stability of an insurance organization allows us to determine that the starting point in determining the essence of financial stability is solvency - "the ability of an insurance company to timely fulfill its monetary obligations, which are based on law or contract." Before discussing the analysis of the main indicators and coefficients that assess the financial stability of insurance companies, it is advisable to highlight the factors that affect it and their main aspects when assessing financial stability. Factors that affect the financial stability of insurance companies can be divided into external (uncontrollable) and internal (controllable) factors in accordance with the general approach.

Table 1

Classification of types of financial stability of insurance companies [1]

Financial stability classification criteria	Types of financial stability of insurance companies
By level of financial stability	Absolute
	Normal (normal)
	Unstable (pre-crisis situation)
	Crisis situation
By time period analyzed	Short-term
	Medium-term
	Long-term
By entity assessing financial stability	Internal (company employees, founders and internal audit)
	External (contractors of the company, financial and credit organizations, financial intermediaries, government bodies, rating agencies, external audit, other physical and legal entities, etc.)
According to the stage of development of the company	Financial stability at the stage of entering the insurance market
	Financial stability in the growth phase
	Financial stability in the development phase
	Financial stability during a downturn
By stages of the	Financial stability in conditions of maximum

economic development cycle	development
	Financial stability in a downturn
	Financial stability in times of crisis

It should be noted that one of the main external factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies is the legal basis of regulation of this system in the country. It is precisely the perfectly developed legal and normative documents of the regulation of the insurance market that ensures the efficient operation of companies based on the implementation of strategic projects, optimal decision-making, and the achievement of financial stability.

Each of the external and internal factors affecting the financial stability of insurance companies has its own characteristics in terms of their impact on the financial condition of the company. If we consider external factors, they do not depend on the insurance company itself, therefore, taking into account the fact that the company cannot change the impact of such factors, it should adjust its financial activities in accordance with external factors. Internal factors, on the other hand, depend on the financial activities of the insurance company, therefore, the insurance company can ensure its financial stability by directly influencing these factors. It should be emphasized that both external and internal factors affecting financial stability have their own characteristics and require a separate approach, but we will dwell on some of them.

Table 2
Financial indicators of the insurance market of Uzbekistan [2]

Indicators	31.12.2022		31.12.2023		Change, %
	in million soums	in % of total	in million soums	in % of total	
Total	2596 926	100%	2022 054	100%	-22,1%
Insurance organizations in the general insurance sector, including:	1 098 782	42%	1 568 461	78%	+42,7%
- compulsory insurance	232 813	9%	236 691	12%	+1,7%
- voluntary insurance	865 969	33%	1 331 770	66%	+53,8%
Insurance organizations in the field of life insurance, including:	1 498 144	58%	453 594	22%	-69,7%
- compulsory insurance	9 332	0%	12 658	1%	+35,6%
- voluntary insurance	1 488 812	57%	440 935	22%	-70,4%

The basis of any economy depends on its sustainable development. In this case, the effective use of insurance institutions is of great importance. In this regard, ensuring the stability of insurance companies is even more important. One of the main factors ensuring the financial stability of an insurance company is the insurance portfolio. Understanding the essence of the insurance portfolio and ensuring its balanced form remains relevant today. The insurance portfolio is the basis that determines the entire activity of an insurance company and its financial stability. The insurance portfolio is understood as the actual number of insured objects or existing insurance contracts in a certain territory. The financial stability of the insurance portfolio is understood as a constant balance between the risks assumed and the profitability of the portfolio. The size, quality, composition and dynamics of the insurance portfolio determine the profitability of insurance operations, the receipt of insurance payments, fluctuations in insurance coverage, and changes in the volume of insurance amounts.

The solvency of insurance companies is understood as the ability to fully and timely fulfill monetary obligations to the insured in accordance with the terms agreed upon in the contract or legislative documents. The solvency of insurance companies is determined based on the characteristics of its sector and industry. In addition, international financial reporting standards and international practice also have specific characteristics of this indicator. In particular, in

accordance with the procedure adopted in the countries of the European Union, the solvency of insurance companies is assessed by comparing its current state with a standard amount (norm) for solvency. In general, the level of solvency of an insurance company should answer the question of what is the sufficiency of private capital by the company to meet its obligations.

List of used literature:

1. Baratova, D., Khasanov, K., Musakhonzoda, I., Abdumuratov, S., & Uktamov, K. (2021). The impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the insurance market of Uzbekistan and ways to develop funded life insurance. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 296, p. 06028). EDP Sciences.
2. Prepared by the author based on information from the official website of the Ministry of Economy and Finance - <https://www.imv.uz/>

